

Trends and Burden of Childhood and Adolescent Cancers in Jos, North Central Nigeria: A Seven-Year Retrospective Registry-Based Study

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Abstract

Background: Childhood and adolescent cancers are a growing public health concern, particularly in low- and middle-income countries where survival rates remain low. Reliable epidemiological data are essential for effective planning and improving outcomes. This study assessed the burden and temporal trends of childhood and adolescent cancers in Jos, north central Nigeria.

Methods: A retrospective review of the Jos University Teaching Hospital cancer registry was conducted for cases diagnosed between January 2017 and December 2023. Children and adolescents aged 0–18 years with confirmed malignancies were included. Data on demographics, cancer type, morphology, and anatomical site were extracted and analyzed using descriptive statistics based on the International Classification of Childhood Cancer, Third Edition (ICCC-3).

Results: Of 3,990 registered cancer cases, 478 (12.0%) occurred in children and adolescents, with a median age of 11 years and a male-to-female ratio of 1.3:1. Childhood cancers (0–14 years) accounted for 8.6% of total cancers, while adolescents (15–18 years) contributed 3.4%. The most common malignancies were rhabdomyosarcoma (20.9%), non-Hodgkin lymphoma excluding Burkitt (10.9%), nephroblastoma (6.7%), acute lymphoblastic leukemia (6.3%), Burkitt lymphoma (5.9%), retinoblastoma (5.4%), and Hodgkin lymphoma (4.8%), together accounting for over 60% of cases.

Conclusion: Childhood and adolescent cancers constitute a significant proportion of the cancer burden in Jos. Emerging trends suggest a shift from historical lymphoma predominance toward increasing solid tumors. Strengthening diagnostic services, establishing a robust population-based cancer registry, and improving pediatric oncology infrastructure remain priorities for reducing the burden and improving outcomes for children with cancer in Nigeria.

Keywords: Childhood cancer, Adolescent cancer, Cancer burden, Cancer trends, Nigeria

Introduction

Cancer is a leading cause of death worldwide, accounting for about 9.7 million deaths in 2022.¹ Childhood cancer constitutes a significant public health problem globally, being the sixth leading cause of cancer burden and the ninth leading cause of disease burden among children and adolescents.² An estimated 400,000 children and adolescents develop cancer annually, with approximately 80% of these cases occurring in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).^{3,4} Survival rates in high-income countries exceed 80% due to comprehensive cancer services; however, less than 30% of children with cancer from LMICs survive.^{5,6} This disparity is largely attributed to delayed diagnosis, misdiagnosis, limited access to appropriate treatment, treatment abandonment, drug toxicity, and disease relapse.^{5,6}

Moreover, most LMICs lack functional cancer registries, making it difficult to accurately assess childhood cancer incidence and outcomes.⁴ This limitation hampers effective policy formulation, resource allocation, and monitoring of interventions.⁴ Given that there are no standardized population screening programs to detect and prevent childhood cancers, enhancing survival in LMICs requires effective planning and strengthened healthcare infrastructure.^{7,8} In Nigeria, childhood cancers contribute significantly to pediatric morbidity and mortality. However, the true burden remains poorly defined due to under-reporting, fragmented data, and the limited number of structured cancer registries.⁹ Challenges such as limited oncology infrastructure, delayed health-seeking behavior, and inadequate diagnostic and treatment services further worsen outcomes.⁵ Although cancer control policies have seen gradual development, paediatric-specific data to inform strategic interventions remain insufficient.¹⁰

Reliable epidemiological data are essential not only for quantifying disease burden and tracking temporal trends, but also for effective planning and improving outcomes. Accurate data supported evidence-based policymaking, resource prioritization, and monitoring of national cancer control efforts are required. Unfortunately, structured paediatric registries remain sparse in Nigeria, contributing to data gaps that limit

contextual planning and action.

This study aimed to address these gaps by generating contemporary, registry-based data on childhood and adolescent cancers in Jos, north central Nigeria. By analyzing cases recorded in the Jos University Teaching Hospital (JUTH) cancer registry between 2017 and 2023, this study assessed both the burden and temporal patterns of paediatric malignancies. Findings from this study are expected to support local and national oncology planning and contribute to broader efforts toward cancer control in resource-constrained settings.

Methods

Study location

This study was carried out at the Jos University Teaching Hospital in Plateau State, north-central Nigeria. The research utilized data from the Hospital's cancer registry, which was established in 2016 with support from a National Institutes of Health (NIH) grant (D43 TW010130). The registry maintains detailed records of both solid tumors and hematologic malignancies diagnosed at JUTH. As of December 2023, it had documented 478 cases involving paediatric and adolescent patients.

Jos University Teaching Hospital is a tertiary healthcare facility situated in Jos and serves as a major referral center for the region. Initially set up as a pathology- and hospital-based registry, the cancer registry has since evolved into a population-based system, now covering a population of approximately 3.5 million people across an area of 26,899 square kilometers.¹¹ The registry actively gathers data from a wide network of public, private and faith-based health institutions within Plateau State and neighboring states.

Study design

This was a cross-sectional study based on a seven-year retrospective review of cancer registry data, conducted to assess the burden and temporal trends of childhood and adolescent cancers.

Study population

Participants were children and adolescents aged 0-18 years diagnosed with cancer whose data were captured in the registry between January 2017 and December 2023.

Sample size determination and sampling technique

All eligible paediatric and adolescent cancer cases recorded in the JUTH cancer registry between January 2017 and December 2023 were included in the study. As this was a total population study, no formal sample size calculation was required. A total population sampling technique was employed, including all cases that met the inclusion criteria. Cases were excluded if they had benign tumors (n = 1), incomplete data (n = 4), or unclear diagnoses.

Data collection

A standardized data extraction proforma was developed by the research team based on variables routinely collected in the JUTH cancer registry and guided by the International Classification of Childhood Cancer, Third Edition (ICCC-3). The proforma was pre-tested for completeness and clarity and was refined to ensure consistency and reliability of data extraction. Two trained research assistants used the finalized tool to extract data from the registry, with all entries cross-validated by the lead researcher.

Extracted variables included age at diagnosis, sex, educational status, year of diagnosis, cancer type, and anatomical site. Cancers were assessed based on both morphologic classification (histological type) and anatomic topography (site of origin), as recorded in the registry. This approach allowed for a comprehensive evaluation of disease burden and distribution. Assessing cancers by morphology and anatomical site is essential for understanding epidemiological patterns, identifying priority areas for diagnostic support, and aligning with global paediatric cancer reporting standards.

Data analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS software, version 23.0 (Chicago, IL, USA). Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, were used to summarize categorical variables. Continuous variables, such as age at cancer diagnosis, were assessed for normality and presented as median with interquartile range (IQR) due to skewed distribution. Cancer cases were classified according to the International Classification of

Childhood Cancer, Third Edition (ICCC-3).¹² The ICCC-3 provides a standardized framework for categorizing childhood malignancies using the International Classification of Diseases for Oncology, Third Edition (ICD-O-3) coding system. It organizes childhood cancers into 12 principal diagnostic groups based primarily on tumor morphology (histologic type) and topography (anatomical site).¹²

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of Jos University Teaching Hospital. The study utilized de-identified data from the JUTH cancer registry, with no direct contact with patients.

Results

Socio-demographic characteristics

As shown in Table 1, a total of 478 children were diagnosed with cancer between 2017 and 2023, with males accounting for 271 (56.7%). The majority were older children and adolescents, particularly those aged 10–14 years (140, 29.3%) and those aged 15 years and above (135, 28.2%). Children under 5 years comprised the smallest group (74, 15.5%), and the median age at cancer diagnosis was 11 years. Patients came from diverse ethnic backgrounds, with Hausa being the most represented group (131, 27.4%), while 114 (23.9%) had unclassified tribal identity. In terms of educational status, most had attained primary education (221, 46.2%), with only 72 (15.1%) reaching the tertiary level, while 43 (9.0%) had no formal education. The highest annual frequency of cancer diagnoses was recorded in 2017 (105, 22.0%), with the lowest in 2023 (32, 6.7%).

Prevalence of paediatric and adolescent cancers and annual distribution

Between January 2017 and December 2023, a total of 3,990 cancer cases (including both adults and children) were registered. Of these, 478 cases occurred in individuals aged 0–18 years, yielding an overall paediatric and adolescent cancer prevalence of 12.0%. Childhood cancers (ages 0–14 years) accounted for 343 cases (8.6%), while adolescent cancers (ages 15–18 years) accounted for 135 cases (3.4%). On average, approximately 68 paediatric cancer cases were diagnosed annually during the study period (Figure 1). Figure

2 illustrates the annual trend of paediatric cancer diagnoses. A peak occurred in 2017, followed by a fluctuating trend through subsequent years, with relative declines noted in 2018 and 2023.

Distribution by Cancer Morphologic Type and Age (ICCC-3 Classification)

Table 2 shows the age-specific distribution of cancer cases according to the International Classification of Childhood Cancer (ICCC-3) morphology classification. The most frequently diagnosed morphologic group was soft tissue and other extraosseous sarcomas, comprising 127 cases (26.6%), of which rhabdomyosarcoma alone accounted for 100 cases (20.9%). Rhabdomyosarcoma occurred predominantly in children aged 5–9 years (35 cases) and 10–14 years (31 cases), with fewer cases in those aged 0–4 years (15) and 15 years (19). Lymphomas and reticuloendothelial neoplasms represented the second most common group, accounting for 107 cases (22.4%). Among these, non-Hodgkin lymphoma (excluding Burkitt) occurred in 52 children (10.9%), mainly within the 10–14 and 5–9-year age groups. Burkitt lymphoma, with 28 cases (5.9%), peaked in the 5–9-year category, while Hodgkin lymphoma was diagnosed in 23 children (4.8%), primarily in those aged 10–14 years (13 cases) and 15 years (7 cases). Nephroblastoma, the most common renal tumor, was identified in 32 children (6.7%), with the highest frequency in the 0–4-year group (18 cases) and the 5–9-year group (11 cases). Retinoblastoma accounted for 26 cases (5.4%), occurring most commonly in children aged 0–4 years (13 cases). Among haematologic malignancies, acute lymphoblastic leukemia (ALL) was the predominant subtype, with 30 cases (6.3%) distributed across all age groups but most frequent in children aged 5–9 years (9 cases).

Together, these seven morphologic types—rhabdomyosarcoma (20.9%), non-Hodgkin lymphoma excluding Burkitt (10.9%), nephroblastoma (6.7%), acute lymphoblastic leukemia (6.3%), Burkitt lymphoma (5.9%), retinoblastoma (5.4%), and Hodgkin lymphoma (4.8%)—accounted for 291 out of 478 cases (60.9%). While these cancers occurred across all age groups, they were predominantly concentrated among children aged 5 to 14 years.

Anatomical distribution of tumors (Topography)

The most frequently affected anatomical site was the lymph nodes, accounting for 82 cases (17.2%), followed by the eye (41 cases, 8.6%), blood (40, 8.4%), and the kidney (33, 6.9%). Other notable sites included the stomach (22, 4.6%), mouth/tongue (21, 4.4%), bones (15, 3.1%), and soft tissues (14, 2.9%). The brain was involved in 11 cases (2.3%), while additional sites such as the ovary, colon/rectum, skin, breast, liver, and nasopharynx each contributed smaller proportions. In 97 cases (20.3%), the anatomical location of the tumor was unclassified or not clearly defined, and therefore categorized as not otherwise specified (NOS). Table 3.

Sex distribution of common morphologic types

The distribution of the seven most frequent cancer morphologies by sex is presented in Figure 2. Rhabdomyosarcoma remained the most frequent, with a marked male predominance (65 males vs 35 females; M:F ratio 1.9:1). Non-Hodgkin lymphoma (non-Burkitt) also showed a male predominance (34 males vs 18 females; ratio 1.9:1), as did retinoblastoma (17 vs 9; 1.9:1) and acute lymphoblastic leukemia (17 vs 13; 1.3:1). In contrast, Burkitt lymphoma and nephroblastoma showed relative female predominance, particularly nephroblastoma (12 males vs 20 females; ratio 0.6:1). Hodgkin lymphoma had the highest male-to-female ratio (17 vs 6; ratio 2.8:1).

Table 1: Socio-demographic characteristics of participants and year of diagnosis (n = 478)

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Sex		
Male	271	56.7
Female	207	43.3
Age Group (years)		
0 - 4	74	15.5
5 – 9	129	27.0
10 - 14	140	29.3
15	135	28.2
Median Age (IQR)	11.0 (6.0–15.0) years	
Tribe		
Hausa	131	27.4
Berom	34	7.1
Fulani	34	7.1
Igbo	26	5.4
Tiv	24	5.0
Yoruba	17	3.6
Unknown	114	23.9
Others*	98	20.5
Educational Status		
No formal education	43	9.0
Primary school	221	46.2
Secondary school	142	29.7
Tertiary institution	72	15.1
Year of diagnosis		
2017	105	22.0
2018	48	10.0
2019	73	15.3
2020	61	12.8

**Mwaghavul, Tarok, Eggon, Ngas, Idoma etc.*

Figure 1. Prevalence of pediatric and adolescent cancers among total registered cancer cases (n = 3,990)

Figure 2. Annual distribution of paediatric cancer diagnoses.

Table 2: Age-Specific distribution of paediatric cancer cases by morphology group (n=478).

Morphology	Number of cases				Total (%)*
	0-4 years	5-9 years	10-14 years	15 years	
I. Leukemias, Myeloproliferative diseases, and Myelodysplastic diseases	9	15	8	8	40 (8.4)
1a. Lymphoid leukemia	8	9	6	7	30 (6.3)
Ib. Acute myeloid leukemia	1	4	2	1	8 (1.7)
Ic. Chronic myeloproliferative diseases	1	1	0	0	2 (0.4)
II. Lymphomas and reticuloendothelial neoplasms	6	35	40	26	107 (22.4)
IIa. Hodgkin lymphoma	0	3	13	7	23 (4.8)
IIb. Non-Hodgkin lymphoma (except Burkitt)	5	16	17	14	52 (10.9)
IIc. Burkitt lymphoma	1	15	9	3	28 (5.9)
IIId. Miscellaneous (composite Hodgkin and Non - Hodgkin lymphoma	0	1	1	2	4 (0.8)
III. Brain and spinal Neoplasms	2	1	6	2	11 (2.3)
IIIb. Astrocytomas	0	1	2	0	3(0.6)
IIIc. Intracranial and intraspinal embryonal tumors †	1	0	3	1	5 (1.0)
IIId. Other gliomas	1	0	0	0	1(0.2)
IIIe. Other specified intracranial/intraspinal neoplasms (meningioma)	0	0	1	1	2(0.4)
IV. Neuroblastoma	3	1	2	0	6 (1.3)
V. Retinoblastoma	13	9	3	1	26 (5.4)
VI. Renal Tumors	18	11	4	1	34 (7.1)
VIa. Nephroblastoma	18	11	2	1	32 (6.7)
VIb. Renal carcinomas	0	0	2	0	2 (0.4)
VII Hepatic tumor (Cholangiocarcinoma)	0	0	0	1	1(0.2)
VIII. Malignant Bone Tumors	0	4	8	8	20 (4.2)
VIIIa. Osteosarcomas	0	3	6	7	16 (3.3)
VIIIb. Chondrosarcomas	0	0	1	0	1 (0.2)
VIIIc. Ewing tumor	0	1	0	1	2 (0.4)
VIIIId – Others ‡	0	0	1	0	1(0.2)
IX. Soft Tissue and Other Extraosseous Sarcomas	19	39	40	29	127 (26.6)
IXa Rhabdomyosarcoma	15	35	31	19	100 (20.9)
IXc. Kaposi sarcoma	1	3	3	2	9 (1.9)
X. Germ Cell Tumors, Trophoblastic Tumors and Neoplasms of Gonads	2	1	1	3	7 (1.5)
XI. Other Malignant Epithelial Neoplasms and Malignant Melanomas	2	9	25	52	88 (18.4)
XII. Other and Unspecified Malignant Neoplasms	0	4	3	4	11 (2.3)
Total	74	129	140	135	478 (100.0)

* – percentage of total number of pediatric cancer cases (n=478), † – Medulloblastoma (4: 3, 10-14; 1, 15), medulloblastoma (1, 0-4) and pineoblastoma (1, 15), ‡ - Malignant giant cell tumor of bone)

Table 3: Distribution of paediatric cancer cases by anatomical Site (Topography) (n=478)

Topography	Frequency	Percent
Lymph nodes	82	17.2
Eye	41	8.6
Blood	40	8.4
Kidney	33	6.9
Stomach	22	4.6
Mouth/Tongue	21	4.4
Bones	15	3.1
Soft tissues	14	2.9
Ovary	13	2.7
Brain	11	2.3
Colon / Rectum/ Anus	9	1.9
Ear/Nose/Throat	9	1.9
Skin	9	1.9
Breast	8	1.7
Peritoneum	8	1.7
Cervix	6	1.3
Bladder	5	1.0
Liver	5	1.0
Nasopharynx	5	1.0
Uterus/Vulva	5	1.0
Thyroid	4	0.8
Small intestine	3	0.6
Testis/Male genital	3	0.6
Adrenal gland	1	0.2
Glands - Other	1	0.2
Prostate	1	0.2
Respiratory tract	1	0.2
Ureter	1	0.2
NOS / Unknown	97	20.3

NOS - Not Otherwise Specified

ALL – Acute Lymphoblastic Leukaemia
Figure 2. Top seven cancer morphologic types by sex

Discussion

This study provides a contemporary overview of childhood and adolescent cancers in Jos, north central Nigeria, and reveals important epidemiological patterns and temporal trends. Paediatric and adolescent cancers accounted for 12% of all malignancies registered between 2017 and 2023. This proportion is higher than the 2.7% reported in a previous study at the same center between 2006 and 2010, where the denominator was total paediatric admissions.¹³ In contrast, the present study assessed paediatric cancers as a proportion of all diagnosed cancer cases (adult and pediatric), thereby offering a broader oncology-centered perspective. When compared with findings from other regions of Nigeria, the burden observed remains substantial. In a study from

south eastern Nigeria, childhood cancers constituted 5.6% of all malignancies, while lower proportions have been reported in Asia (e.g., 4.4% in Bangladesh and 3.6% in India), and about 0.8% in the United States.¹⁴⁻¹⁷ The relatively higher burden of paediatric cancers in sub-Saharan Africa has been partly attributed to demographic characteristics, notably a younger population structure.¹⁸

Our center recorded approximately 68 new paediatric cancer cases per year, which is notably higher than previously reported figures from the same location, with 23 and 17.4 cases per annum,^{13,19} as well as from Uyo in southern Nigeria, where an average of 10.4 cases per year was documented.

²⁰ This difference may reflect improvements in

registry completeness, broader population coverage, improved case detection, and heightened public awareness of cancer services over time at our institution. The socio-demographic profile of the patients in this study mirrored patterns observed across other Nigerian regions. We found a slight male predominance, consistent with findings from Nnewi, Uyo, and other centers across Nigeria.^{14, 20, 21} Some studies suggest that cultural factors and preferential healthcare-seeking behavior for male children may partly explain the trend.^{14,20}

The age distribution revealed the highest frequency in the 10–14 years age group, followed closely by the 5–9 years group, reflecting the epidemiology of malignancies such as rhabdomyosarcoma, non-Hodgkin lymphoma, and nephroblastoma, which are common in middle childhood and early adolescence. A particularly striking finding from our study was the emergence of rhabdomyosarcoma as the most common paediatric malignancy. This finding aligns with the earlier observations by a study in Jos where a predominance of rhabdomyosarcoma among solid tumors was reported.¹⁹ However, it contrasts with findings by another study in the same location where Burkitt lymphoma was documented as the most common childhood malignancy, representing 48.9% of cases.¹³ Similar trends favoring Burkitt lymphoma were documented in Uyo and other centers across Nigeria.²⁰⁻²²

The rise of rhabdomyosarcoma may reflect evolving disease patterns, improvements in diagnostic accuracy (especially for histologically confirmed solid tumors), and possibly a real shift in epidemiology. Some studies have suggested that the burden of Burkitt lymphoma may be declining, possibly linked to improvements in malaria control — a key factor in the etiology of endemic Burkitt lymphoma.^{20, 23} As malaria transmission decreases, the epidemiological dominance of Burkitt lymphoma may be waning, allowing other cancers such as sarcomas and nephroblastoma to become more prominent. A similar trend was noted in Nnewi, where nephroblastoma and rhabdomyosarcoma rose in prominence over time.¹⁴

Comparative analyses across regions further

underscore the geographic variations in childhood cancer distribution. In northern Nigeria (e.g., Kano), Burkitt lymphoma has historically been the most prevalent paediatric malignancy, although retinoblastoma has also been reported with notable frequency.^{21, 24} In contrast, centers in southern Nigeria such as Ibadan and Sagamu have historically reported a predominance of lymphomas, with nephroblastoma also featuring among the more common paediatric malignancies.^{23,25} In comparison, our findings from Jos reveal an emerging epidemiologic pattern marked by rising frequencies of rhabdomyosarcoma and nephroblastoma, alongside the continued burden of haematologic malignancies. These regional differences emphasize the need for locally tailored strategies to improve childhood cancer detection, diagnosis, and management across Nigeria.

In our series, lymphomas (especially non-Hodgkin and Burkitt lymphoma) remain the second most common group after soft tissue sarcomas. Nephroblastoma (Wilms tumor) ranked third, followed by acute lymphoblastic leukemia and retinoblastoma. While hematologic malignancies like ALL were present, their proportion remained lower than in high-income countries, where leukemias account for approximately 30% of childhood cancers.¹⁷ Central nervous system tumors were rare in our cohort, similar to observations across sub-Saharan Africa, likely due to diagnostic limitations and possibly genuinely lower incidence.^{14,21,26} Notably, Kaposi sarcoma accounted for a small proportion of cases (1.9%) in our series, consistent with its relatively low occurrence among paediatric malignancies in West Africa.²⁷ Although Kaposi sarcoma was historically more prevalent during the peak of the HIV/AIDS epidemic, particularly in East and Southern Africa, its incidence in our cohort was low, possibly reflecting improved HIV control efforts and regional epidemiological differences.²⁷

The anatomical distribution of tumors mirrored the observed morphologic patterns. Lymph nodes were the most commonly involved site, followed by the eye, blood, kidney, and gastrointestinal tract. The relatively high proportion of lymphoid malignancies further corroborates the high rates of lymphomas and hematological cancers in this

population. In terms of sex distribution of cancers, most of the leading cancer types showed a male predominance, especially rhabdomyosarcoma, non-Hodgkin lymphoma (non-Burkitt), retinoblastoma, and Hodgkin lymphoma. Conversely, nephroblastoma exhibited a female predominance, consistent with patterns described in other West African studies.

Taken together, our findings highlight both consistencies and evolving trends in childhood cancer epidemiology at JUTH compared to previous decades. Improvements in diagnostic capabilities, greater clinical suspicion, the establishment of a cancer registry, and increased public health awareness campaigns may all have contributed to the higher case capture seen during the study period. Nonetheless, childhood cancers continue to pose significant challenges, especially regarding early diagnosis, access to treatment, and long-term outcomes. Despite the insights gained, this study has limitations. Being a single-center, hospital-based retrospective review, it may not capture the full burden of childhood cancers in the region, especially among children who never access tertiary care. Reliance on registry data means that cases with incomplete or missing information could have been misclassified. Moreover, outcome data were not analyzed in this study, an important next step for fully characterizing the paediatric oncology burden. Nonetheless, the study has several strengths. It is one of the few contemporary, registry-based assessments of childhood and adolescent cancers in Nigeria, spanning a seven-year period and utilizing a standardized classification system (ICCC-3). The use of both morphologic and anatomic classifications enabled a comprehensive and detailed analysis of cancer types. Moreover, the inclusion of temporal data provides insights into evolving epidemiological patterns, making the findings valuable for local and national cancer control planning. The robustness of the dataset further strengthens the reliability of the results.

In conclusion, childhood and adolescent cancers represent a significant proportion of the cancer burden at Jos University Teaching Hospital. Our findings demonstrate an evolving pattern from historical lymphoma predominance to increasing frequencies of soft tissue sarcomas and renal

tumors. These shifts may reflect broader epidemiologic transitions linked to infectious disease control, improvements in cancer diagnostics, and changing healthcare access. Strengthening diagnostic services, establishing a population-based cancer registry, and improving paediatric oncology infrastructure remain priorities for reducing the burden and improving outcomes for children with cancer in Nigeria.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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